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Abstract— Medicanes represent a unique weather phenomenon in the Mediterranean Sea, combining features of both tropical and extra-tropical cyclones. The recent Mediane Helios induced a severe windstorm that caused storm surges and flooding impacting coastal regions of southeastern Sicily. To assess the hydrodynamic parameters, such as tide phase, storm surge and wave flow induced by Mediane “Helios”, an innovative machine learning system called LEUCOTEA was used. This system takes into account a combined approach of Geomorphological surveys, Convolution Neural Network, and Optical Flow techniques with real-time video records. The system provides the values of tide phases, storm surge and wave flow that could be useful for policymakers and environmental managers as a valuable tool to assess the potential coastal risks and to develop appropriate mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Keywords— Neural Network; storm surge; flooding; tide phases; wave height.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mediterranean hurricanes, known as “medicanes” [1], are a meteorological phenomenon that combines features of tropical and extratropical cyclones [2]. They can cause severe impacts on coastal regions, such as heavy rainfall, storm surges, and flooding [3]. The frequency and intensity of these events have been increasing [4], making it important to understand and predict their behaviour [5]. A mediane named “Helios” caused significant damage to coastal ecosystems and infrastructure in the eastern coast of Sicily in February 2023. Recent advances in machine learning and deep learning techniques have been applied to assess the catastrophic impacts of Medicanes and to improve the forecasting accuracy [6]. Many improvements of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) were obtained in the video monitoring field for coastal application [7]–[9]. Optical methods are also used to obtain high-frequency data, to identify contrasting surface features to act as targets that are assumed to move from frame to frame. Foam represents the main target to track the wave propagation within the surf zone through Optical Flow [10]. Moreover, optical images will also sense light reflections from sloped water surfaces and turbidity that alters background water colors [11]. Furthermore, alongshore currents are estimated by extracting alongshore pixel time stacks from video [12], [13]. This study focuses on the application of deep learning methods, specifically CNN and Optical Flow, for the real-time video monitoring, in order to assess tide and storm parameters during Mediane Helios occurrence. Coastal video

monitoring represents a low-cost tool for data collection with high-frequency temporal resolution [14]. Moreover, machine learning and deep learning techniques have been used to automatically process data obtained through video monitoring. Previous studies have focused on using optical images to extract hydrodynamic properties of nearshore waves and currents [15], but these methods often require supervised image feature selection and data transformation. With the development of deep learning techniques, supervised feature selection is no longer required, and it is possible to automatically analyze large amounts of data [16]. CNNs are widely used for image segmentation, classification, including object and face recognition [17]. In the field of video monitoring, CNNs can obtain low-frequency data of sea motion such as tide and storm surge. To obtain high-frequency data, Optical Flow techniques are used to identify contrasting surface features that change from frame to frame. In this work, a monitoring system called LEUCOTEA was used to assess tide, wave, and storm parameters from video records using a combination of CNNs and Optical Flow techniques in the MATLAB environment. The system was used to study the effects of the recent Mediterranean hurricane, Helios, on the Ionian coast of Sicily and could be used as an innovative approach to early warning systems for similar events in the future.

II. GEOGRAPHICAL SETTINGS

In the present study, the Ionian coast of south-eastern Sicily has been chosen to assess storm surge during Mediane Helios. The coastline has a geographical extent of about 300 km (Figure 1) and experiencing significant coastal retreat, with a shoreline erosion rate of approximately -5 m/year [18]. This erosion is caused by a combination of natural processes, such as wave erosion, storm surge, and sea-level rise, as well as human activities like building and sand mining [19]. The alternating small rocky promontories and pocket beaches along the coast make it particularly vulnerable to erosion during high-energy storm events [20]. The effects of tsunamis and storms on the coastal area has been observed, with evidence of significant coastal erosion and inundation [21]. The Mediterranean cyclones are phenomena that are increasing with ongoing climate changes, and are determining erosional effects on the southeastern Sicily coasts. According to Miglietta et al., [22] and Tous and Romero [23], medicanes are distinguished from Mediterranean cyclones by their visual resemblance to tropical cyclones in satellite imagery.

Within this definition, a Mediterranean cyclone can be classified as a medicane if it shows a cloud-free area with a central ‘eye’ surrounded by bands of spiral clouds [24], [25]. Fita and Flaounas[26] studied Medicane Zeo (December 2005) and suggested that medicanes are hybrid systems which may exhibit features of both tropical and extratropical cyclones, and can be classified as part of the wider category of subtropical cyclones [27]. The medicanes displayed features which were similar to those of tropical systems for a short period after their formation, whereas they highlighted extratropical features in the majority of their tracks [22], [28]. The horizontal extension was generally a few hundred kilometres and their intensities reached values comparable to a Category 1 on the Saffir-Simpson hurricane wind scale [29]. Medicanes usually occur once or twice a year between September and January [3], [27], [30], [31].

These storms are characterized by high winds, heavy rainfall, and high waves, and can cause significant damage to coastal areas. Recent studies showed that medicanes have been increased in frequency and intensity, causing stronger effects when compared to common seasonal storms [3]. In recent years, several medicanes have strongly affected the coast of southeastern Sicily causing significant coastal erosion and flooding. Unlike tropical cyclones, medicanes form through a process called Tropical Transition (TT), which occurs when an extratropical system transforms into a tropical system or a hybrid cyclone [27]. The Ionian Sea, where southeastern Sicily is located, is not typically an area eligible for the formation of tropical cyclones. However, the TT process can initiate the formation of medicanes in the region. Despite the forecasts highlighted that the frequency of medicanes in the Mediterranean region will decrease due to climate change[32], but their impacts are expected to become more severe. Rising sea surface temperatures and changing atmospheric conditions may make it easier for medicanes to form and intensify. Therefore, it is crucial to continue preparedness and adaptation measures in coastal areas of southeastern Sicily, such as the construction of coastal defense structures, restoration of natural coastal features, and development of emergency response plans and early warning systems, to help minimize the impacts of future medicanes on coastal communities and infrastructure.

III. MATERIAL & METHODS

The LEUCOTEA system has four phases: (a) defining the video dataset, (b) acquisition of field data, (c) analyzing the video using CNN and (d) Optical Flow techniques. The system investigates tide and wave parameters using deep learning and Optical Flow with video records from fixed remote-controlled cameras at the coast of Santa Lucia (along the coastal stretch of study area reported in Figure 1). The video dataset was chosen from the webcam data acquired from 8 February 2023 to 11 February 2023 (impact of Medicane Helios).

Field data was obtained using a phase-shifting Laser Scanner Faro Focus X130 to generate point clouds and GPS-RTK acquisitions to geo-reference and adjust for geodetic elevation.

The CNN used in this work is based on the assumption that it is possible to assign a tide value for each video frame recorded by webcam. The architecture of the CNN requires the tide

classes to represent the tide phase during the acquisition of the video frames.

Figure 1. Study area of southeastern Sicily affected by Medicane Helios impact.

The classification network architecture follows the ResNET50 model and was developed in a MATLAB environment (Figure 2). The CNN assigns a tide value to each video frame from a global training set of over 3200 images is used. The video frames are analyzed with a continuous series of layers of three types: convolutional layers (Convolutional and Conv Block), pooling layers (Max and Avg Pool), and fully connected layers (FC). The convolution is combined with an activation function called Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), generally the ReLU activation layer. ReLU is a piecewise linear function that returns 0 if it receives any negative input, but for any positive value x , it returns that value. Thus, it provides an output with a range from 0 to infinity. Pooling layers allow for reducing the picture dimension, also referred to as subsampling, by taking the mean or the maximum on patches of the image (Avg Pool or Max Pool). The CNN ends with a fully connected layer, where each element of the previous layer is connected to the *softmax* layer. The *softmax* layer provides the most probable values of tide phases and storm surges.

Figure 2. CNN structure for the assessment of tide phases and storm surge.

The CNN results were validated with data recorded by a tide gauge sensor located almost 40 km away from the coastline (Figure 3, tide gauge of Porto Palo di Capo Passero). To represent tide phases over time, different image frames were extracted from the video records and tide classes were associated with each image.

Figure 3. Sea level measured through tide gauge at Porto Palo di Capo Passero.

A dense Optical Flow module was applied to extract the wave features, following the same approach of Wu et al.[11]. The Optical Flow assessment is based on the object motion estimation observed between consecutive video frames caused by the relative movement between the object and camera, considering the Farneback algorithm. Considering the pixel $I(x, y, t)$ within a frame of an image, the pixel has moved by a certain distance (dx, dy) in the next frame, taken in the time increment dt . Farneback algorithm provides the flow vectors in x - y directions, the magnitude of flow vectors, and the vectors' orientations. The square root of the magnitude of flow vectors represents the wave flow on the water surface. The dimensional units of flow vectors are expressed in pixel/frame. To convert the pixel/frame units in meters/second, the Terrestrial Laser Scanner data were used to obtain the dimensional grid on the water surface.

IV.RESULTS

Time-series of storm surge and tide values were assessed through the CNN applied on the video frames. The CNN achieved an accuracy of 83.61% with a Categorical Cross Entropy Loss function. The CNN predictions were compared with actual tide signal values recorded by tide gauge through RMSE analysis, which showed a RMSE of 0.12 m. A three-order polynomial interpolation was applied to the tide values obtained from the CNN to reproduce tide phases. The results were compared with the actual tide data which revealed that the extreme values of about 1m (Figure 4a), as predicted by the deep learning method, occurred just before the occurrence of Medicane Helios.

Optical Flow was used to obtain wave flow vectors for each video frame recorded by surveillance camera. These wave flow vectors were then used, with the Airy linear theory, to obtain the tensors of wave heights for the area. An RMSE analysis was performed to assess the error between the wave height assessed through the linear theory and reference points assessed throughout the TLS data, showing an error of 0.1 m. The Optical Flow is used for continuous extraction of wave heights from the video records impacting the coasts. The wave break heights were automatically extracted, and the results showed the greatest wave heights of about 4 m captured in the webcam of Santa Lucia (Figure 4b).

a)

b)

Figure 4. Meteo-marine parameters assessed for the Medicane Helios; a) CNN predictions compared with tide records; b) wave height extracted from a time-series of continuous video record.

Meteo-marine parameters assessed for other Medicane Zorbas and Medicane Apollo in the work of Scardino et al.[6] highlighted similar values of storm surge and wave height during the occurrence of Medicane Helios. Furthermore, the storm surge observed during Medicane Helios resulted greater than storm surge experienced during common seasonal storms.

Considering the issues connected to the climate changes, the evaluation of the meteo-marine parameters requires data with a high areal distribution. Within this framework, the webcam distributed along the coasts could represent a low-cost tool for the assessment of meteo-marine parameters. On the other hand, the effects of medicanes are increasing and several studies are investigating their hydrodynamic characteristics [31], [33]–[35]. An integration of video monitoring with other methods, like detection of medicane tracks through remote sensing technologies [31], [33], [36], could improve the early warning systems for the medicane occurrence.

V.Conclusion

The application of machine learning for the video monitoring allowed us to assess the meteo-marine parameters during the occurrence of Medicane Helios. This kind of approach represents a low-cost tool for the assessment of storm surge and wave parameters through the video monitoring. In our case of study, CNN allowed to classify the tide values and storm surge from the video frames, while the Optical Flow allowed to assess the wave parameters from continuous video records.

The main results obtained through video monitoring during the occurrence of Medicane Helios were:

- Medicane Helios highlighted storm surge values greater than common seasonal storms impacting in southeastern Sicily;
- The wave heights were found to be comparable with the medicanes occurred in the last decades, like Medicane Zorbas and Medicane Apollo.

Applications of CNN and Optical Flow could be a useful tool for the early warning systems during the occurrence of hurricanes and medicanes.

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